

Welcome to the Move2THz Newsletter #1!

February 2025

Stay up to date with the recent progress, key milestones, and exciting updates from the Move2THz team!

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Main Highlights of This Edition

Exciting project start and Kick-Off meeting;

Productive and impactful Workshop in European Microwave Week 2024;

Engaging interviews with PhD students working on the project;

Cutting-edge scientific Book with Move2THz publications;

High-profile international dissemination events (in France, Japan, Germany, Belgium, etc.);

Let's explore further!

About Project

Sustainable INDIUM PHOSPHIDE (InP) Platform and Ecosystem Upscaling, Enabling Future Mass Market (sub-)THz Applications.

Move2THz – an ambitious project that will address today's InP shortcomings and build a mature European ecosystem to obtain a commercially and industry-viable platform for use in various mass-market applications utilizing the higher frequency spectrum towards THz and beyond.

Main objectives:

1)

Provide a competitive facility for high-volume InP manufacturing in Europe that is ready to use in the industry.

2)

Foster and leverage the European ecosystem on InP from the material to the application and widen the market adoption.

3)

Demonstrate an overall CO2 footprint reduction all along the product life cycle, from cradle to grave.

Breaking Frequency Barriers for Next-Gen Applications

Move2THz project is breaking the frequency wall to enable industry-viable next-generation applications by providing a sustainable technology platform & related ecosystem covering the entire value chain.

Meetings and Events

Project Kick-Off Meeting

09-10/07/2024

Bernin, France

Video

The project-leading company, Soitec, invited all 27 partners to Bernin, France, to officially kick off the Move2THz project activities, clarify roles and responsibilities, and discuss risk management. The event started with an inspiring introduction by our Project

Coordinator, Francois Brunier, and continued by laying the groundwork for our next steps with insightful discussions and collaborative efforts. After a cozy social event evening at the edge of the Alps, all partners successfully transitioned into an intensive technical session, where the primary objectives included outlining the project's technical roadmap, addressing potential challenges, aligning on key deliverables, and fostering collaboration among team members to ensure seamless execution of the technical aspects of the project.

The group's work will focus on establishing a robust European supply chain and a cutting-edge manufacturing ecosystem for Indium Phosphide (InP) semiconductors. Innovative InP technologies deliver unprecedented speeds and energy efficiency, crucial for future applications like AI mega data centers to 6G mobile communications and beyond.

Move2Thz Co-organised Workshop in the European Microwave Week

22/09/2024

Paris, France

Move2Thz

Scientific Book

Video

The first major project dissemination campaign took place during the European Microwave Week in Paris 2024 – the largest and most comprehensive conference in Europe dedicated to the field of microwaves. Project partners participated in networking opportunities and delivered presentations in a co-organized workshop titled "Key Enabling Technologies for Future Wireless, Wired, Optical, and Satcom Applications". This workshop was a collaborative effort with another Horizon Europe project SHIFT (project No. 101096256). The workshop featured 28 insightful presentations divided into five thematic groups, covering key topics such as substrate technology innovation, high-speed communication circuit design, and

disruptive system integration for future (sub-)THz and optical applications.

Key outcomes from this event included a workshop **wrap-up video** and **The Scientific Book** which features 8 peer-reviewed publications from Move2THz consortium (River Publishers). This book presents the latest research roadmaps and achievements from the European ecosystem (industry, research, and academia) driving the development of future wireless, wired, optical and satcom applications utilizing the mm-wave and sub-THz bands. It covers the entire value chain, including technologies, devices, characterization, architectures, circuits, 3D heterogeneous integration and packaging.

Dissemination Event: TThinkNet 6G Summit

17/10/2024

Munich, Germany

Move2THz coordinator Francois Brunier participated at the ThinkNet 6G Summit, organized by Bayern Innovativ GmbH, in Munich, Germany. Our project was presented highlighting sustainable European solutions, energy-efficient technologies in smartphones, cutting-edge chip advancements, and strategies to reduce the carbon footprint in chip

manufacturing. With a presentation titled "IPCEI ME/CT for sustainable European solutions in the connectivity market". The event brought together over 165 industry professionals and students, including experts in 5G telecommunications, 6G standardization and artificial intelligence, as well as Bavarian, Saxon and federal public authorities (BMBF).

Photo Credits: Bayern Innovativ GmbH, Ivonne Wagner.

Dissemination Event: Brabant Innovation Days

13/11/2024

Tokyo, Japan

This November, the Dutch Province of Brabant, one of Europe's leading high-tech regions, hosted the 5th Brabant Innovation Day at The Okura. This annual summit has become a beacon for showcasing the latest innovations from Brabant's startups, research institutes, and regional government, all working together to address global challenges. The Move2THz project was mentioned by our scientific partner, Eindhoven University of Technology, in Associate Professor Yuqing Jiao's presentation - "Next-Generation PIC Research at TU/e". Presenting TU/e's vision for the future scaling of the PIC technology, especially in speed, energy efficiency, and integration density.

13-14/11/2024

Lille, France

Dissemination Event: RF-Net Network Workshop

The Move2THz partner, IMS Laboratory, participated in the first RF-Net network workshop held by the Institute of Electronics, Microelectronics, and Nanotechnology (IEMN) on the topic of radio frequency calibration. These technical days were an opportunity to present this new network of radiofrequency characterization platforms and to create a moment of exchange between its members. Assoc. Prof. Marina Deng (IMS Laboratory) presented Move2THz-related research on "THz transistors in III-V technology for 6G applications: how to measure them to envision the circuits of the future?".

First Project General Assembly meeting

03-04/12/2024

Lille, France

The Move2THz partners convened for the 1st General Assembly meeting at the esteemed Institute of Electronics, Microelectronics, and Nanotechnology (IEMN), located in the picturesque city of Lille, France. Held over two highly productive days (December 3-4, 2024), the consortium reviewed project updates and charted the course for the next six months. The meeting featured a dynamic agenda, including: evaluating the project's progress to date; reflecting on activities undertaken during the initial six months; addressing challenges by identifying key achievements and areas for

improvement; strategizing the next critical steps for the initiative.

Additionally, an on-site meeting of the Work Package leaders was conducted to align our priorities. On the second day, two pivotal workshops were held, one focusing on WP4 specifications and the other on the selection of technical KPIs, followed by a highlight of the day — exploring the cutting-edge facilities of IEMN, where walking through the characterization platforms and clean room (via the visit corridor) was both fascinating and inspiring, showcasing where innovation truly lives.

Dissemination Event: EF ECS 2024

05-06/12/2024
Ghent, Belgium

The Move2THz team participated in a premier event that fosters collaboration and innovation in the electronics and systems community—EF ECS 2024 in Ghent, Belgium. The project had its personal exhibition booth in the Sensors and Devices category. It was a great opportunity to meet new researchers, partners with topic-related projects, or industry leaders at the same event. Additionally, project coordinator Francois Brunier participated in the EF ECS discussion “Chips for Europe Initiative: Strengthening EU Competitiveness” and shared insights on our ongoing contributions.

EF ECS is dedicated to advancing Europe’s strategic leadership in semiconductor technology. This year’s event emphasised the Chips Joint Undertaking’s pivotal role in addressing societal and industrial challenges while fostering collaboration and innovation across the EU.

Dissemination Event: IP-SoC Conference 2024

10/12/2024
Grenoble, France

Move2THz project was presented at IP-SoC 2024 Conference – project coordinator Francois Brunier discussed on "Increased Competitiveness and Sustainability in Connectivity with Advanced Substrate Solutions," highlighting innovative approaches to drive efficiency and eco-friendly advancements in the connectivity industry. D&R IP-SoC Days are unique worldwide events fully dedicated to IP (Silicon Intellectual Property) and IP-based Electronic Systems.

Exploring the Future: Interviews with Move2THz PhD Students

In this interview, Mr. Moussa Cissé, a PhD researcher at IMS – Laboratory for the Integration from Material to Systems (University of Bordeaux, France), shares insights into his doctoral research and its connection to the Move2THz project.

“I have always been fascinated by the potential of high-frequency semiconductor technologies. InP, in particular, due its exceptional electron mobility and high breakdown voltage, making it ideal for high-speed and high-power applications (Radio Frequency and Millimeter Wave).”

Mr. Moussa Cissé
IMS Laboratory

His work focuses on advancing Indium-Phosphide (InP) double heterojunction bipolar transistors (DHBTs), a crucial technology for enabling next-generation mobile communications, including 6G. We also discuss the technical challenges he faces working on the project, his professional growth, and the broader opportunities in the semiconductor industry, particularly in the field of sub-THz communications.

Can you describe your doctoral research topic/area and how it relates to the Move2THz project?

My doctoral research focuses on “On-wafer RF characterization of Indium-Phosphide (InP) double heterojunction bipolar transistors (DHBTs)” through a collaboration with both III-V Lab and ETH-Zurich. This work aligns closely with the objectives of the Move2THz project, which seeks to leverage the high-frequency capabilities of InP technology and combine it with the large-scale integration potential of silicon platforms to enable the next generation of mobile communications (6G). Then, the InP device characterization represents an indispensable step, which intends to extract key parameters such as f_T (transition frequency) and f_{max} (maximum oscillation frequency), essential metrics for building compact models that facilitate the design of high-performance RF circuits.

What personally inspired you to take the chance to work on these technologies and on this project?

I have always been fascinated by the potential of high-frequency semiconductor technologies. InP, in particular, due to its exceptional electron mobility and high breakdown voltage, making it ideal for high-speed and high-power applications (RF & mmW). I am excited to work on this project for its ambition to contribute to the European leadership in 6G technologies by addressing the challenges of sub-THz communication.

Which organisation are you working with on the Move2THz project? Can you describe your role within the team and your primary responsibilities?

I am working in the “Model for Circuit” team, which is included in the “Circuit Design” research group in the IMS Laboratory (Integration from Material to System). My role in the team mainly concerns the RF characterization of InP devices, focusing on the extraction of

their high-frequency performance metrics (f_T , f_{max}) and high-frequency noise parameters. I am also responsible for the design of RF test structures by using EM simulation predictive capabilities and low-noise amplifier (LNA) circuit block design as demonstrators for sub-THz applications.

Who do you collaborate with most often, and what does that collaboration look like?

I collaborate frequently with researchers and professors who are experts in RF characterization. While I perform a significant portion of my work independently, particularly the experimental and simulation aspects, this independence is complemented by regular discussions and feedback sessions with team members to ensure alignment with the broader objectives of the Move2THz project.

What specific technical or professional skills have you developed through this job?

On-wafer RF characterization of active and passive devices, S-parameter measurement, high frequency noise measurement, Passive test structures design and modelling, EM simulation and RF/mmW circuits design.

What has been the biggest challenge in your role so far, and how did you address it?

One of the challenges I have encountered is the accurate extraction of RF performance parameters (such as f_T and f_{max}) from the measurement data, particularly at high frequencies. To address this, I optimized the de-embedding techniques used during on-wafer measurements, and refined the design of test structures to minimize parasitic effects (inductances and capacitances). This iterative process ensures more reliable data and models for circuit design.

Semiconductor technologies evolve rapidly. How do you stay updated with new advancements?

To stay informed about advancements in semiconductor technologies, I regularly read articles from journals like IEEE, participate in seminars and workshops organized by IMS Laboratory, work on open source projects related to semiconductors technologies, and follows industry leaders' social medias.

What do you see as the most significant challenges and opportunities in the semiconductor industry over the next decade?

One of the most significant challenges will be the scaling of semiconductor technologies to meet the demands of 6G and beyond, particularly in terms of sub-THz performance, energy efficiency, and integration with existing platforms. At the same time, this presents an opportunity to explore innovative materials, such as InP and Gallium Nitride (GaN), and hybrid solutions that combine the benefits of III-V semiconductors with silicon.

What do you think - why Move2THz findings are/will be important to Europe?

By combining the strengths of InP and silicon technologies, the Move2THz project will enable the development of cost-effective, high-performance solutions for sub-THz communication. This will not only bolster Europe's position in the global race for 6G, but also contribute to building a resilient and competitive semiconductor ecosystem that supports the broader goals of technological sovereignty and innovation within the European Union. Moreover, the project has significant environmental implications. The InP-based devices offer a promising pathway to more energy-efficient solutions, which is critical for achieving Europe's climate goals and reducing CO2 footprint all along the product life cycle, from cradle to grave.

In this interview, **Mr. Francesco Fortunato, working on the Move2THz project at Chalmers University of Technology (Sweden)**, reflects on the rapid evolution of semiconductor technologies and emphasizes the importance of continuous learning through research papers and hands-on experience.

Mr. Fortunato shares insights into his role at Chalmers, detailing responsibilities such as conducting research, developing hands-on lab expertise, and collaborating with supervisors and colleagues.

“It hasn’t been easy to learn the manual skills required to work in the cleanroom and the lab, as it requires precision and a full understanding of the entire process.”

Mr. Francesco Fortunato
Chalmers

Can you describe your doctoral research topic/area and how it relates to the Move2THz project?

My PhD focuses on the fabrication of semiconductor devices for Terahertz applications. In particular, my work for Move2THz is related to the fabrication and analysis of indium phosphide (InP) High Electron Mobility Transistors (HEMTs) on silicon substrates. Within the project, I try to successfully

demonstrate these devices on the structures that have been built by partners using the SmartCut technology to transfer InP on silicon and epitaxial growth of the heterostructure. This means that I am involved with cleanroom work (where we fabricate the devices) and in the measurement lab. (I want to note that I started my PhD only a handful of months ago, so I don’t have the full expertise in both labs.)

What personally inspired you to take the chance to work on these technologies and on this project?

Since my first course in electronics during my engineering degree, I discovered that I really enjoy solving problems in the semiconductor technology, because it really puts together electronics and physics and I think this is the best and most interesting area to study and research on when it comes to engineering. The PhD position is directly connected to Move2THz, and it's definitely exciting to be inserted into such a project.

Which organisation are you working with on the Move2THz project? Can you describe your role within the team and your primary responsibilities?

I am working at Chalmers University of Technology in Göteborg, Sweden, as part of my PhD studies. My role, as any PhD student, is to become an independent researcher and to produce contributions in the field of semiconductors by reading and eventually writing papers. This is done by discussing and presenting results to my supervisors and colleagues. Apart from striving to get a substantial baggage of theoretical knowledge through courses at the university, I also plan to get as much hands-on experience as possible within the labs we have at Chalmers.

Who do you collaborate with most, and what does that collaboration look like?

I mostly collaborate with my supervisors and my colleagues at Chalmers. That mostly includes discussions and meetings about our topics of research, scientific papers we've read and doubts and challenges we run into in the cleanroom and in the lab. This happens regularly, but most of the time, I work independently by studying something new or working towards better understanding of my own devices. Moreover, I expect to have more fruitful discussions with other partners involved in Move2THz as time goes on.

What specific technical or professional skills have you developed through this job?

I've learned a lot in these few months of my PhD, such as how to correctly read a paper, how to make concise presentations that show results that others can immediately understand, and, in general, what my responsibilities are as a PhD student at Chalmers. Other important abilities that I'm still learning are the manual skills required to work in the cleanroom and in the lab: this hasn't been easy since it requires precision and full comprehension of the whole process.

What has been the biggest challenge in your role so far, and how did you address it?

The biggest challenge has been the adaptation time to learn notions and skills that were totally new for me and not to forget very advanced and complex to understand: it's still a challenge every day. Being quick in understanding concepts in the field and prioritizing my tasks is essential for a smooth workflow, and those have been and still are crucial to master to this day.

Semiconductor technologies evolve rapidly. How do you stay updated with new advancements, and can you describe a situation where you had to quickly learn a new concept or technology?

I try to stay updated by reading papers that have been recently published in the field, and I also make use of the library to get access to new and even old books to revise or become competent in something that I think could be useful in my own work or just catches my curiosity. As an example, I got to learn HEMTs (High Electron Mobility Transistors) and cleanroom practices in these few months since the start of my PhD, and while I'm still far from being able to say that I have completely mastered them, I admit I've been learning immensely, also thanks to the support of my colleagues. It also helps (for me at least) to write down

what I've just learned as well as repeating it on my own multiple times.

What do you see as the most significant challenges and opportunities in the semiconductor industry over the next decade?

In my opinion, the challenge is the need for sustainable production of wafers while at the same time obtaining greater performances for the applications that need ever-increasing requirements in the field of telecommunications and electronics. Surely, this could result in a trade-off among the many parameters and figures of merit, but I am hopeful that progress can be made within Move2THz. Optimizing such processes is definitely not straightforward, but it could be very rewarding in the future.

What do you think - why Move2thz findings are/will be important to Europe?

For starters, InP is a material with properties that have great potential for building cutting-edge electronic circuits, and I feel that the solutions and collaborations that come out of Move2THz will move forward the development of devices in Europe that make use of InP. This might come from a more viable implementation of the growth of the materials and optimized fabrication of the devices, as many partners are doing, or from an improved comprehension of the mechanisms inside semiconductors. Either way, I am confident this can make InP more affordable and thus more accessible for industries in all kinds of fields.

Publications and Articles

First Press Release Widely Spread

Emmanuelle Bely, Soitec General Secretary

"This project marks a key milestone in the integration of ever more powerful and energy-efficient semiconductor technologies. Together, we are paving the way for innovation based on indium phosphide that will transform critical sectors such as 6G telecommunications, photonics and artificial intelligence. Furthermore, it fully embodies our shared ambition to create a strong and autonomous European ecosystem capable of meeting the technical and economic challenges to large-scale adoption of these cutting-edge technologies."

Press Release

After issuing this press release, Move2THz project has been covered by a wide range of international and French semiconductor news platforms. I.E.:

,Semiconductor Engineering' comprehensive weekly review of the latest developments and trends in the semicon industry, including Move2THz: <https://semiengineering.com/chip-industry-week-in-review-52/>

,Semiconductor Today' about us: https://www.semiconductor-today.com/news_items/2024/sep/-soitec-move2thz-100924.shtml

Move2THz Open-Access Scientific Publications

Publication, Chapter in the Book "B55X: A SHIFT in STMicroelectronics BiCMOS Technologies"; Pascal Chevalier (STMicroelectronics), Frederic Giancesello (STMicroelectronics), A. Gauthier, N. Guitard, V. Milon, F. Monsieur, N. Derrier, C. Deglise-Favre, D. Céil, C. Durand, O. Foissey, F. Sonnerat, F. Giancesello, D. Gloria. https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C1.pdf

Publication, Chapter in the Book "Advanced Substrate Technologies for Sub-THz Era"; Francois Brunier (Soitec). https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C3.pdf

Publication, Chapter in the Book "RF Technology Roadmap for 5G and 6G RF Front-end Systems"; Yvan Morandini (Soitec). https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C2.pdf

Publication, Chapter in the Book "A CMOS Compatible III-V-on-300 mm Si Technology for Future High-speed Communication Systems: Challenges and Possibilities"; Abhitosh Vais (imec), Bruno Ghyselen (Soitec), A. Kumar, G. Boccardi, S. Yadav, Y. Mols, R. Alcotte, B. Vermeersch, M. Ingels, U. Peralagu, C. Roda Neve, B. Parvais, P. Wambacq, B. Kunert, and N. Collaert. https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C4.pdf

Publication, Chapter in the Book "Challenges for 2.5D and 3D Integration of InP HBT Technology"; Bertrand Ardouin (III-V Lab), Romain Hersent (III-V Lab), Tom K. Johansen, Antoine Chauvet, Virginie Nodjiadjim, Agnieszka Konczykowska, Nil Davy, Muriel Riet and Colin Mismar. https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C18.pdf

Publication, Presentation abstract published in the Book "InP on Si Technologies for NextGeneration Optical Communication High-speed Analog Front-Ends"; Romain Hersent (III-V Lab). https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C5.pdf

Publication, Presentation abstract published in the Book "Heterointegration Approaches for InP-HBT Technologies for 5G Applications and Beyond"; Hady Yacoub (Ferdinand-Braun-Institut). https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C16.pdf

Publication, Presentation abstract published in the Book "SiGe BiCMOS & III-V Technologies Heterogeneous Integration Challenges"; Frederic Giancesello (STMicroelectronics). https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/chapter/RP_9788770046640C19.pdf

The Open-access Book PDF. https://www.riverpublishers.com/pdf/ebook/RP_E9788770046640.pdf

Upcoming Events

**2nd project General
Assembly meeting**

Brussels, Belgium

**31/06-01/07
2025**

**1st Year Project
Review Meeting**

Brussels, Belgium

**02/07
2025**

**Move2THz organised
workshop in ESSERC 2025**

Munich, Germany

**08-11/09
2025**

Move2THz

Key Facts

Duration	Start date	Number of partners	Total budget	EU budget contribution
36 months	2024 06 01	27	€ 40,67 M	€ 11,96 M

Discover More Extensive and Up-To-Date Information on Our Website

move2thz.eu

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